

ВИБІР СПОСОБУ ЛАПАРОСКОПІЧНОЇ ТА ВІДКРИТОЇ АЛОПЛАСТИКИ ПРИ ЗАЦЕМЛЕНИХ ПАХВИННИХ ГРИЖАХ

CHOICE OF SURGICAL APPROACH IN CASE OF INCARCERATED INGUINAL HERNIA REPAIR: LAPAROSCOPIC AND OPEN

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Background. Operations for incarcerated inguinal hernias are one of the most common operations performed in general surgery. The results of treatment of incarcerated inguinal hernias remain unsatisfactory, mortality from pinched inguinal hernias is 10-25%. Causes of mortality are late medical treatment, intestinal necrosis, and necrosis of the omentum, failure of the anastomosis, peritonitis. Among the unsatisfactory results of wound healing are wound infection, a high recurrence rate. Reducing the frequency of recurrences is possible due to the wider use of alloplasty, both open and laparoscopic. The question of the choice of laparoscopic or open alloplasty for incarcerated inguinal hernias remains undeveloped.

Purpose: To increase the effectiveness of surgical treatment of incarcerated inguinal hernias by justifying the choice and improvement of open and laparoscopic alloplasty.

Materials and methods. The analysis of the surgical treatment of 40 patients with incarcerated inguinal hernias is carried out. The age of patients is 20 to 75 years. The average age was 56.1 ± 1.2 years. There were 5 women and 35 men. Depending on the method of surgical treatment, patients were divided into two groups. In group I (20 patients) - surgical treatment was performed according to an improved new algorithm, which includes diagnostic laparoscopy with further dissection of constriction ring and assessment of intestinal viability and execution of transabdominal preperitoneal inguinal hernia repair. In group II (20 patients) - the traditional method of open anterior hernia repair was performed. In the postoperative period, the frequency of postoperative complications and recurrences of inguinal hernia was assessed.

Results and discussion.

Immediate results of surgical treatment of incarcerated inguinal hernias among patients of group I (main) group (n=20) showed that in the early postoperative period no wound complications were present. Among patients of group II (comparison) hematoma of the postoperative wound was observed in 1 (5%), suppuration of the postoperative wound was found in 1 (5%), and chronic postoperative pain was diagnosed in 1 (2%). Long-term results of surgical treatment of inguinal hernias were studied by repeated examinations and questionnaires over the period of 1 to 3 years. Among 20 patients of group I recurrences of inguinal hernia were not detected, and among patients of comparison group 2 (10%) recurrences were diagnosed. The obtained results showed higher efficiency of surgical treatment in patients of the main group, which was achieved through the use of the newly developed algorithm.

Conclusion. Introduction of the developed algorithm of laparoscopic alloplasty of incarcerated inguinal hernias, in comparison with traditional open anterior inguinal hernia repair, improves treatment results, reduces the frequency of complications of the surgical wound, and reduces the frequency of recurrences.